

Editorial

Theology of Education and Philosophy of Education in Dialogue

Zuzana Svobodová

Dear readers,

We are introducing the journal *Theology and Philosophy of Education*, a journal for theology of education and philosophy of education. The reason for establishing this journal is to create a common platform for theologians, philosophers, and educators, but also for all helping professionals, who ask about the aim of human life, self-education and education, ethics, humanity, and how people from different cultures, nations, languages, who are living today more and more together could also together search or seek ways of life, ways of truth.

For the abbreviation of the journal-title, we chose TAPE. Of course, it is because **Theology And Philosophy of Education** should be connected here. However, one can also hear about “taping” today. In this way, to tape means also to heal, help, harmonize, or regenerate, relieve, reconcile, and remedy. We want to connect different approaches to the education of man. In the old Greek sense, “to harmonize” means connecting and combining opposites even though they remain distinct or diverse. In Greek mythology, Harmony (Harmonia) was the daughter of the god of war, Ares, and the goddess of love, Aphrodite. It means the two opposite dynamics were connected, and then Harmonia was born. In TAPE, we value differences, variety, and diversity. On the website of this journal, you can read articles which authors have written in diverse scientific fields. It is not apparent that philosophers, medical doctors, businesspeople, and theologians can meet in one professional journal. In TAPE, we want to build bridges between too many separated scientific approaches and communicate together, not only to seek a better future for humans but also to pursue wisdom. It means our aim is not only to pursue, conduct, and practise together with professionals from various backgrounds but also, to see, listen to, and accept in theory (theoria) together with talented or gifted in different respects, ways, or aspects.

By establishing TAPE, we desire to learn from each other and co-create an educative environment where diversity means an opportunity and not a mistake that should be corrected. However, in TAPE, we also want to ask about the truth *behind* all our differences, not only *subsequently* that have scientific variety.

To start publishing a journal also means connecting writers and readers. In TAPE, we have an international editorial board to unite and combine approaches, cultures, manners, and styles for living, not just writing and reading, together, not only next to each other. By writing about the

meaning of education or the sense of life, one is interconnected not only with one's own situation and position but also with the others and can ask the questions: Who will be the readers? How do they live in similar or in very different situations? What will they say? Which questions will they see as the most vivid from their positions? And most importantly, will they understand what we can see and what we are trying to show?

TAPE wants to recognize theology of education as seeking the sense of faith, which is connected with self-education and education – or it is not theology. In his *Theology of Agape*, Josef Zvěřina, the Czech theologian of the 20th century, stated that *theologia* must broaden itself in *theophilia* (*Teologie agapé* I, 5). Likewise, philosophy of education is a way of life linked with self-education and education – or it is not philosophy.

In this first TAPE issue, we offer an interview with Professor Karel Skalický, the chief editor of an exile journal during the communist totalitarian era. In the first reviewed article, Filip Hlavinka seeks opportunities and boundaries of religious and spiritual speech and a significant role of poetry in education. Bert Meeuwsen presents Meaning-Oriented Reflection or MORE3.1.2 as a challenge not only for educators and teachers. Tereza Pinkasová described in her article how moral development could be supported in courses for medical students. František Štěch, knowing that *nobody can drink alone from the well of life*, provides an inspirational vision of dialogue between two theological disciplines if they find not only teaching but also learning aspects of themselves. By reflecting on theology of education, Stuart Nicolson identifies and briefly explores the theme of growing closer to God as well as how Christians can learn to communicate the faith as found in the Vatican II document on education.

Welcome to the TAPE environment; I wish your reading could be healing, inspirational, and gratifying, as well as bracing, restful, and recreative.

Reference

Zvěřina, Josef. 2003. *Teologie Agapé*. Edition 2., (in Vyšehrad 1.) Vol. I. Prague: Vyšehrad.

PhDr. Zuzana Svobodová, Ph.D.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5151-056X>

Charles University, University of South Bohemia

Theology and Philosophy of Education

editor in chief

svobodova@tape.academy